
A comparative analysis of employee wellbeing practices implemented in information technology companies & automobile companies in Pune

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ABSTRACT

In the current unprecedented times of pandemic & BANI environment, maintaining & taking care of employee wellbeing became one of the prerequisites of organizational success. The purpose of this study was to analyze the diverse employee well-being strategies used by the IT & manufacturing industries. The author adopted the methodology of collecting data from 118 respondents working in IT & manufacturing industries using a standardized questionnaire containing standard scales. Focus group interviews with employees were also undertaken to learn more about the different strategies used by companies for promoting employee wellbeing. The analysis produced findings showing that firms view good employee well-being practices as one of their strategic pillars for attracting and keeping talent. The study also highlighted the limitation: The data for the study was collected from the IT & manufacturing sector, so inferences have limitations

KEYWORDS: Employee Well-being, Information Technology, Automobile, life wellbeing, psychological well being.

1. INTRODUCTION

The phrase "employees' well-being" is one that "everyone understands the meaning of yet nobody can define precisely" (Lyubomirs, 2001). According to Ryan and Deci (2001), there are two main philosophical viewpoints on well-being: one is happiness-oriented (i.e., hedonism), which defines well-being as the subjective experience of happiness; the other is eudemonism, which focuses on realizing human potential power and views well-being as the outcome of self-actualization, self-positioning, or personal achievement. The majority of recent studies on wellbeing have agreed that these two unique paradigms were valid. Diener, Ryan, and other members of their team (such as Diener & Ryan, 2011) adopt the hedonistic attitude and use it to advocate for the SWB research methodology. According to several other

researchers (such as Ryff and Singer, 2008), the PWB research approach has developed from eudemonism.

2. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To assess the efforts taken by the IT and Automobile companies to maintain employee wellbeing
2. To study the differences in the responses of employees of the Manufacturing industry and IT industry with regard to employee wellbeing

3. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Being a generic term with a clear definition, "wellbeing" is described as the sensation of health, happiness, and riches. It encompasses feelings of life happiness, mental wellness, and a sense of purpose (Tchiki Davis, 2019). It is linked psychologically to the meaning of life, mastery, optimism, and life happiness. (Millstein, Hippel, et al., 2019; Rudel-Fitzgerald, C.) It is typically described as a condition of positive affective bliss combined with optimal efficacy in one's personal, professional, and social spheres of existence. (2008) Deci & Ryan; (2009) Huppert The phrase "well-being" at the workplace is synonymous with the wellbeing of the workers. It is the employees' physical and emotional well-being at work, or more generally, it is their health and safety.

Research on general well-being topics like SWB and PWB gave rise to and evolved into studies on EWB (Ilies et al., 2007). Currently, most academics describe the idea and implications of EWB for their individual research projects and within their own theoretical frameworks. EWB has not yet been given a standardized action to promote general health can definition or way to be measured.

Much earlier research claims that general well-being is not a good indicator of well-being at work (e.g., Rice et al., 1980; Rode, 2004). Several authors, including Daniels (2000) and Warr (1990), contend that context-specific metrics. To fully understand the nuances, complexity, and variety of employees' cognitive and affective experiences at work, measures of well-being are required. A further suggestion made by Page and Vella-Brodrick (2009) was to use both work-related actions to promote general health can provide an accurate assessment of Employee well-being.

Page and Vella-Brodrick conducted a review of the literature on mental health and wellbeing (2009) have claimed that SWB, PWB, work-related effects, and job satisfaction should all be considered when calculating EWB. According to a study by Wright, Cropanzano, and Bonett (2007), which revealed that job happiness was a reliable predictor of performance, they advocate integrating job satisfaction as one of the EWB's aspects. with EWB reducing the impact of this (operationalized as context-free effect). Daniels' (1990) and Warr's Work-related PA and NA from the (2000) Model of Affective Well-Being give evidence that work-related effects also help with EWB forecasting. Page and Vella-Brodrick (2009) argued that Daniels' approach might complement SWB measurements in addition to work satisfaction.

Employee well-being has long been a top priority for employers and has consistently been the subject of research for a variety of reasons. The well-being of the employee is at risk due to changes in the workplace and society (Guest, 2011), which present significant problems for HR (Guest, 2017). The primary objective of workforce management, in the eyes of HR professionals, is employee well-being. Peccei (2013). Based on the welfare of the employee, performance-oriented HR policies support organizational commitment and job happiness. According to Van De Voorde et al. (2012), autonomy, incentive-based working, teamwork, and a caring attitude from HR support the growth of employee wellness and trust.

4. HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY

1. Employee Well-being practices have a significant impact on the organizational performance.

2. There are significant differences in the responses of employees of the Automobiles sector and IT sector with regard to employee wellbeing.

5. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Exploratory in nature, the study sought to discover how employees felt about employee wellbeing policies and how they affected the organization's performance as a whole. Through a formal letter of request asking for permission for the research, the directors and VP-HR of 10 firms in the manufacturing and IT sectors were approached. Five organizations—three in the IT and two in the manufacturing sector—granted permission after assuring themselves that the investigation was academic in nature. 150 employees received the structured questionnaire in the mail and those who didn't respond received follow-up letters two weeks later. 118 employees completed questionnaires, with a 78% response rate. 54 % of men and 46% of women made up the sample. Focus group interviewing was another effective and qualitative strategy employed by the researcher to comprehend the efforts made.

TABLE 1: DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE OF THE RESPONDENTS

Demographic Details	Particulars	No. of Respondents
Gender	Male	64
	Female	54
Experience	Total	118
	1–3 years	16
	3–5 years	36
	Above 5 years	66
	Total	118
Education	Graduation	74
	Post-Graduation	44
	Total	118

RESEARCH INSTRUMENT

A structured questionnaire was designed comprising 18 questions. The employee wellbeing scale developed by Zheng et al.(2015) was used. The employee well-being scale has 3 components i.e.& Psychological well-being (PWB), life well-being (LWB), and workplace well-being (WWB). The measures used a five-point Likert scale response format. (Ranging from 1-strongly disagree to 5-strongly agree). By calculating Cronbach Alpha, the scale's internal consistency was evaluated. Table II lists the items, their factor loadings, and Cronbach's alpha values.

TABLE 2: RELIABILITY STATISTICS ITEM WISE

Factor names	WWB	LWB	PWB
Cronbach's α s (subscales)	0.79	0.82	0.74
Cronbach's α s (EWB)	0.78		

6. FINDINGS OF THE STUDY AND DATA ANALYSIS

TABLE 3: MANN-WHITNEY U-TEST

Output for Mann-Whitney U-Test			
Variable	Industry	N	Mann-Whitney (U)
Life well-being (LWB)	Automobile	40	.342
	IT	68	.541
Workplace well-being (WWB)	Automobile	40	.423

	IT	68	.807
Psychological well-being (PWB).	Automobile	40	.609
	IT		.441

The hypothesis (H2) that there were significant differences between the responses of the employees of the two sectors, namely the automobile industry and the IT service sector, was evaluated using an independent group Mann-Whitney U-test. The Mann-Whitney U-test findings are shown in Table III. At a 5% threshold of significance, every variable is significant. As a result, theory 2 is disproved. As a result, there are no appreciable variations between the replies of workers in the IT service sector and the automobile industry in relation to a group of variables that make up employee wellbeing. Employees' perception of employee well-being practices is the same throughout the sectors. Thus, hypothesis 2 is rejected.

7. DISCUSSION

According to this study, businesses should make an effort to consider each individual employee's needs and expectations for workplace policies that promote employee health. During the study, it was discovered that employees' expectations of policies for employee well-being are the same regardless of whether they work for an IT firm or a Manufacturing company. Compared to manufacturing companies, IT companies are more strictly adhering to their policies. Particularly strong in IT firms are practices connected to life well-being (LWB) and workplace well-being (WWB). Manufacturing companies are committed to communicating with their staff about issues that may affect their psychological well-being (PWB). It is recommended to Manufacturing companies to consider the life well-being of their employees as this definitely results in better organizational performance. Employee well-being related to the workplace will be maintained better if healthy communication & relations exists between employees and management. In fact, it is recommended to all companies that they should appreciate their employees & take care of their psychological well-being. Considering the amount of job stress & VUCA environment, especially in the IT sector, it is imperative to look after the psychological well-being of employees to make them feel valued. Hence, it is recommended to IT companies that they should pay attention to the psychological well-being of employees. Finally, sound employee well-being practices would ultimately help organizations retain talent & improve the performance of an organization.

8. CONCLUSION

According to recent research, all organizations—regardless of their industry need to increase the adoption of employee wellbeing policies. In the future, organizations that consider it a strategic human resource approach will be more successful and sustainable. This finding demonstrates how better organizational performance can be achieved by ensuring good employee welfare. Employee definitions of well-being and expectations of their employers are the same whether they work in the service industry or the manufacturing sector.

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